

SELECTION OF HIGH TEMPERATURE TOLERANT SPRING WHEAT GENOTYPES USING DNA MARKERS

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Annotatsiya. *Tadqiqotimizda yuqori haroratga chidamlilik bilan genetic bog'langan DNK belgilari (Wmc161, Xcfa2147, Xgwm335 va Xgwm30) yordamida bahorgi bug'doy genotiplarida genetik polimorfizmlarni aniqladik. Ushbu markerlatning allell holatiga asoslanib, biz keyingi seleksion yondashuvlarda foydalanish uchun yuqori haroratga chidamli bug'doy navlarini tanlab oldik.*

Kalit so'zlar: *bahorgi bug'doy, yuqori harorat, chidamlilik, DNK markeri, polimorfizm.*

Аннотация. *В нашем исследовании мы идентифицировали генетические полиморфизмы в генотипах яровой пшеницы с использованием ДНК-маркеров (Wmc161, Xcfa2147, Xgwm335 и Xgwm30), связанных с толерантностью к высоким температурам. На основе аллельного статуса этих маркеров мы отобрали сорта пшеницы, толерантные к высоким температурам, для использования в дальнейших селекционных подходах.*

Ключевые слова: *яровая пшеница, высокая температура, устойчивость, ДНК-маркер, полиморфизм.*

Abstract. *In our study, we identified genetic polymorphisms in spring wheat genotypes using DNA markers (Wmc161, Xcfa2147, Xgwm335, and Xgwm30) associated with high-temperature tolerance. Based on the allelic status of these markers, we selected high-temperature tolerant wheat varieties for use in further breeding approaches.*

Keywords: *wheat, high temperature, tolerance, DNA marker, polymorphism.*

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of the most widely consumed food crops worldwide. In 2020, global wheat production amounted to 772.64 million tons. To maintain the area under cultivation and meet the global demand for wheat, current yields need to increase from 3.3 t/ha to 4.7 t/ha by 2050 [1]. However, various ecological impacts, such as increased temperatures and drought, have led to stagnation in wheat yields and a decline in harvest quality. Rising temperatures and CO₂ concentrations frequently cause heat stress and severe drought in crop fields. By 2050, global wheat production could decrease by approximately 29% due to ecological impacts arising from climate change. In contrast, demand for wheat is expected to increase by 60% by 2050 [2].

Several studies have identified genetic markers for heat resistance in wheat. Maslahetdin et al. (2021) studied the resistance of various wheat strains to stress, including high temperatures, using molecular markers [3]. The markers identified in their research can be used in wheat

selection. Yildiz et al. (2022) aimed to identify functional markers indicating wheat's heat tolerance in their study [4]. Their results confirm the existence of such markers and their significance in selection.

Building on this previous research, one of the most important and effective solutions to these problems is the identification of abiotic and biotic stress-resistant wheat varieties using DNA markers and the implementation of marker-assisted selection (MAS). The main objective of our research is also to identify heat-resistant wheat samples using DNA markers.

Materials and Methods

Plant materials. In this study we have used 25 spring wheat cultivars and lines (Table 1) provided from CIMMYT and ICARDA.

Table 1.

Research samples

№	The name of the plants	Conditional name
1	BCN/WBLL1/ /ROLF07/3/BORL14	L232
2	BCN/WBLL1/ /ROLF07/3/BORL14	L233
3	SOKOLL/3/PASTOR/ /HXL7573/2*BAU/4/WBLL4/	L234
4	REDING/QUAIU	L236
5	REEDLING-GL5A_2/QUAIU	L237
6	MEX94.27.1.20/3/SOKOLL/ /ATTILA/3	L238
7	BCN/WBLL1/4/MILAN/KAUZ/ /DHARWAR DRY/3	L254
8	REEDLING-GL5A_1/QUAIU	L257
9	QUAIU/BORL14	L258
10	REEDLING-GL5A_1/QUAIU	L259
11	№84\2017	L010
12	№85\2017	L013
13	№153\2017	L009
14	КП-2№20\2021	L018
15	КП-2№45\2021	L017
16	КП-2№57\2021	L016
17	КП-2№103\2021	L019
18	КП-2№104\2021	L015
19	Қибрай №2	L021
20	Қибрай №9	L022
21	Қибрай №10	L023
22	Қибрай №31	L025
23	Қибрай №65	L026
24	Қибрай №95	L028
25	Қибрай №97	L029

DNA Markers. Based on the analysis of scientific articles, a DNA marker panel genetically linked to the heat resistance traits of wheat was formed (Table 2).

Table 2

DNA Marker Panel Genetically Linked to Heat Resistance in Wheat

№	Marker	Forward primer	Reverse primer	Tolerant allele	Reference
High Temperature Resistance Markers					
1	Wmc161	acctctttgggatggaagtaa	gtactgaaccacttgaacgca	200	Barakat et al., 2012
2	Xcfa2147	tcatcccctacataaccgga	atcgtgcaccaagcaataca	300	Khan et al., 2021
3	Xgwm335	cgtactccactccacacgg	cggccaagtgtactcttc	250	Barakat et al., 2012
4	Xgwm30	atcttagcatagaagggagtggg	ttctgcaccctgggtgat	160	Barakat et al., 2012

Genomic DNA isolation. The genomic DNA from the fresh wheat leaves were isolation using CTAB method.

PCR Analysis. The PCR assay was conducted using ready mixture of “PCR ScreenMix” (cat. PK041L, Evrogen, Russia) kit.

Gel Electrophoresis. The PCR amplicons were visualized using gel electrophoresis and genotyped using GelAnalyzer 19.

Results and Discussion

To molecularly confirm the heat resistance of this sample, we conducted studies using DNA markers genetically linked to this trait. PCR analysis was performed to study the polymorphism levels of the wheat samples using primers ordered for this purpose. The PCR results were captured using a 2.5% agarose gel on a T100™ Thermal Cycler (BIO-RAD) device (Figure 1).

Figure 1. PCR screening of wheat samples with DNA markers genetically linked to heat resistance. **1-L009, 2-L010, 3-L013, 4-L015, 5-L016, 6-L017, 7-L018, 8-L019, 9-L021, 10-L022, 11- L023, 12-L025, 13-L026, 14-L028, 15-L029, 16-L232, 17- L233, 18-L234, 19-L236, 20-L237, 21- L238, 22- L254, 23- L257, 24-L258, 25-L259.**

The Wmc161 marker has a 200-bp allele identified in 5 varieties in a homozygous state, meaning these varieties possess two copies of this allele. In 3 varieties, it was found in a heterozygous state, indicating the presence of different alleles. This allele was absent in all remaining varieties.

Xcfa2147 marker has a 300-bp allele identified in 2 varieties in a homozygous state and in 11 varieties in a heterozygous state. The remaining 12 varieties do not have this allele.

Xgwm335 marker has a 250-bp allele identified in 22 varieties in a heterozygous state and in 1 variety in a homozygous state. This allele is absent in 2 varieties.

Xgwm30 marker has a 160-bp allele present in 19 varieties, with 12 in a homozygous state and 7 in a heterozygous state. This allele is absent in 6 varieties.

Conclusion

Our results indicate that complex genetic mechanisms contribute to heat resistance in wheat. These DNA markers can be used in breeding programs to develop new wheat varieties with high yields and stress resistance.

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